

Original Research

The Role of Parasocial Interaction in Impulse Buying Behavior in Social Commerce Instagram Considering Social Class and Generation

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Abstract

According to the results of recent studies, the reasons for impulse purchases differ between social classes and different generations. Factors affecting impulse buying behavior in the context of parasocial interaction, including related social features, social class and generation, can be used to provide effective marketing strategies to enhance online impulse buying and help buyers control their impulse buying behavior. The present study investigates the effect of parasocial interaction on impulse buying behavior by considering related social features, and moderating role of social class and generation. The statistical population of the study was comprised of people active in Instagram page in the field of fashion. From among whom 474 completed questionnaires were gathered using the available sampling method. Structural equation modeling in SmartPLS software was used to test the hypotheses. The results of the hypothesis tests showed that social features have a positive impact on the parasocial interaction and parasocial interaction has a positive impact on the impulse buying behavior. Social class and generation have a moderating role in the relationship between the parasocial interaction and the impulse buying behavior.

Keywords: Generational analysis, impulse buying behavior, parasocial interaction, social class.

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Introduction

Marketing literature shows that with the increasing number of social networking users in Iran, social commerce via online businesses is used as a suitable platform for impulse marketing and purchasing (Xiang et al., 2016). Consumers prefer to buy things online due to its convenience motive. Online buying is preferred because it offers a large portfolio of opportunities to select and access full information (Akram et al., 2018). Various researches in the United States stated that impulse buying behaviour of the customers adds up to 80% of all shopping in certain product groups, and it has also been found that purchasing of new products result more from impulse buying than from prior planning (Kalose, 2019) and Extant research emphasizes the role of the purchase experience, that is, psychological benefits attained from the impulse purchase experience itself, as a reinforce of impulse buying (Spiteri Cornish, 2020).

In some research on factors affecting impulse buying, especially in cyberspace, empirical findings suggest the impact of parasocial interaction formed in the context of social commerce on impulse buying (Dong Hee Shin, 2014; Yu et al., 2013; Turban et al., 2011; Wang & L, 2011; Iyengar et al., 2009). This is because social commerce provides a context to support interactions in an online environment and support customer demand for goods and services on the Internet through the web and social technologies (Bianchi & Andrews, 2012). The context of parasocial interaction is formed under the influence of related social features in the context of social commerce, including three dimensions of other users' expertise, liking other users, and likeness of other users (Xiang et al., 2016). According to Turban et al. (2011), social commerce guides interactions between users. Because with the leverage of those social technologies that allow specialist users discuss and provide the right opinion about product benefits, features and uses, sellers enable buyers to influence one another in the buying process (Chen et al., 2013).

A review of the literature also shows that the generation and social class gaps are also determinants of impulse buying. Cultural change is gradual and reflects a transformation in the constructive experiences that have been shaped by different generations. With the succession of younger generations, the worldview, demands, needs and behaviors of audiences have changed across generations. Therefore, it is necessary to consider the different generational attitudes that underlie their different purchasing behaviors and to tailor marketing activities. Undertaking marketing activities without regard to the intergenerational value gap does not have a favorable impact on audiences of different generations, as audiences of different generations derive their value priorities from the institutions and communities around them as well as from personal experiences and apply them for evaluation and developing prescriptive attitudes, norms, and behaviors. Therefore, the personal values that govern each generation influence the buying behavior of that generation (Crawford & Gregory, 2015). On the other hand, consumers of different classes have different preferences for spending money. The consumer social class can be considered the cause of purchase and consumption. Studies have shown that the reasons for purchasing differ from one class to another (Ciunova-Shuleska, 2012; Baker & Hart, 2008). But little research has been done on the impact of the social class on the tendency to impulse buying. According to what has been said, the present study has two main objectives. First, an attempt is made to develop a model explaining the relationship between parasocial interaction and impulse buying behavior within the social network

context of Instagram. Second, it is aimed to explore the moderating role of social class and generation in the relationship between parasocial interaction and impulse buying behavior. Since social commerce is an emerging trend in Iran, further research in this field is an undeniable necessity. Impulse buying is also an important research topic among consumer behavior researchers not only because of its complexity, but because of its widespread use in a wide range of product segmentations. A review of the literature also shows that in previous research on the determinants of impulse buying, little attention has been paid to the impact of generational and social class gaps on impulse buying behavior. Only a few studies have been conducted in recent years in the field of generational analysis, including research by Pentecost and Andrews (2010) and Khan et al. (2016). Makmor et al. (2024) in their research was seek to understand the influence of para social interaction (PSI) in live-streaming shopping affects consumers impulsive buying in live-streaming platforms using the Stimulus Organism Response (SOR). A self-administrative questionnaire survey was conducted, and 335 valid responses are useable. The survey was validated by using Smart PLS technique to conduct direct and mediating effects. The result revealed that the relationships between social commerce, social presence, narrative involvement, parasocial interaction, and impulsive buying behaviour are significant. The parasocial interaction acts as mediation effect between the social factors, and impulsive buying on the live-streaming website. Sheruly and Koentary (2023) aim to investigate how self-control and financial literacy might mitigate the influence of parasocial relationships on impulse buying tendencies, with the ultimate goal of preventing individuals in early adulthood from getting trapped in the cycle of impulsive buying and its long-term ripple effects. Participants in this study are 195 women aged 18 to 25 who have a favorite celebrity figure and had purchased beauty products in the previous two months. According to the findings of simple regression analysis, parasocial relationships affect impulsive purchasing tendencies ($F(1.191) = 12.100, p < .05, = .059, = .054$). It was also discovered that self-control has a moderating role on the influence of parasocial relationships toward impulse buying tendencies ($R = .4172, F(1.191) = 13.4189, p < .05$), but financial literacy has no moderating role. The study of Gupta and Lingam (2023) aims at identifying factors which lead to impulse buying behaviour among customers while shopping online. Study is conducted in Bhubaneswar with 416 young respondents who are online shoppers. For analysis 33 variables were put under study, out of which 10 relates to impulse buying behaviour and other relates to reason for impulse buying and post purchase disposition of impulse buying. Factor analysis technique is applied to 23 variables which extracted 8 factors for impulse buying behaviour of consumers. Regression analysis was used test the effectiveness of extracted factors in predicting dependent factor impulse buying. All 8 factors found to be predictors of impulse buying behaviour with significant f value of 0.00 and r square value of 0.932. Limitations of the study remains with small sample relating only to youth population of Bhubaneswar. Study can be extended to larger sample and effect if different moderators can also be taken into account like age, gender, income level. The study will help both academicians and practitioners to identify, understand and implement the factors in future. The research of Triyoga and Objectives (2023) tests relationships between interaction communication, expertise knowledge, Self-congruity parasocial relationships, and Impulse Buying. One hundred seventy samples were used, of which the Retrieval sample used purposive sampling. Research results show that the five hypotheses are accepted: interaction communication, self-congruity, and parasocial relationships influence impulse buying. Interaction communication and self-congruity are influential towards parasocial

relationships. One hypothesis is rejected: expertise knowledge does not impact parasocial relationships.

Therefore, conducting a research that examines a set of situational, psychological, social, and intergenerational factors to investigate impulse buying behavior in Iran, as one of the most important developing countries with emerging markets, can address ambiguities regarding impulse buying behavior in the context of social commerce in developing countries, thereby providing researchers with the opportunity to examine the validity and applicability of theories developed in Western and developed countries in countries with different cultures and conditions. Little research has been done on the concept of generational analysis, class analysis, and parasocial interaction, as the main drivers of impulse buying. The purpose of the authors of this article is to examine the simultaneous impact of social class and generation on the relationship between parasocial interaction and impulse buying behavior. In this study, the research hypothesis is first formed by studying the theoretical foundations and research background. In the following, the research method and hypotheses testing will be reviewed. Finally, the conclusions of the research findings will be presented.

Literature Review and Hypothesis Development

Impulse Buying Behavior

Impulse buying refers to sudden, unplanned purchases. Impulse buying is positively associated with the impulsive attribute of consumer decisions. Online impulse buying emphasizes purchases that break down the rational boundaries of the purchasing process and occur in a very short time without evaluating the multiple alternatives and weighting implications, largely after the individual is influenced by an internal or external stimulus (Nazari, and Baghdadi, 2013). Chart1 shows the number of articles published during different years. As it is evident in the chart1, only one article was published in 1979 in the field of "impulsive buying behavior" until 2000, when this subject has been gradually noticed by researchers, and the trend of publishing articles from 2011 to 2014 is an upward trend and then it has a downward trend until 2021 and an increasing trend again in 2022 and this shows the increasing importance of studying in this field.

Chart 1. The number of articles published during different years in the field of "impulse buying behavior"

Social Commerce

There are so many definitions of social commerce so far, all of which have the same meaning. In one of these definitions, social commerce is the use of social media in the field of e-commerce to assist the online purchase and sale of goods and services (Sau-Ling, 2010). Social commerce has emerged from the integration of different fields. The major emphasis of social commerce is to combine social activities with online marketing and sales. Thus, social commerce is closely linked to the concept of social marketing introduced in 1970 as an approach to planning social change aimed at improving the quality of life (Turban, 2011). Social marketing involves the scientific and practical areas of business activity. Thus, social commerce can be considered as a subset of social marketing that deals with online sales. Recently, the term social marketing has changed and is being used synonymously with social media. Another root of social commerce includes web business applications, which include social networking and the use of social software, such as blogs and wikis. The other roots of social commerce are communication and collaboration theories, virtual societies and the virtual world; finally, its main root is e-commerce (or e-business) with different business models (Turban et al., 2011).

Social Features and Parasocial Interaction

According to Xiang et al. (2016), related social features in the social business context include three dimensions of other users' expertise, liking other users, and likeness of other users. Other users' expertise is the level of competence and awareness of the users and the correct opinion of the resources required. Likeness of other users is the degree to which people who interact with each other have similar beliefs, education, social status, and so forth. Also, in an initial encounter, if they perceive that the person who is the source of the information has desirable or positive attributes, they are more likely to find that source to be liked and persuaded by the information sent from that source (Rogers & Bhowmik, 1970). Previous communication research supports the importance of similarity in the development of parasocial relationships. Kelman (1961) believes that since expert opinions are more reliable and valid than non-experts, so users in the social business context tend to consult more with an expert and shape their attitude with regard to views of experts (Xiang et al., 2016). Dong Hee Shin (2014) showed that the power of online experience and friendship enhances the formation of parasocial interaction. As a result, users from inactive information consumers have become active partners in producing content. They naturally share information, and then reach a group agreement through interactions and communications. So according to the explanation of the first to third hypothesis, it can be stated as follows:

H₁: Other users' expertise in the social business context has a positive impact on the Parasocial Interaction.

H₂: Liking other users in the social business context has a positive impact on the Parasocial Interaction.

H₃: Likeness of other users in the social business context has a positive impact on the Parasocial Interaction.

Parasocial Interaction and Impulse Buying Behavior

With the advent of social, the change occurred in some of the communication habits online. This world of constant communication is a challenge for businesses as well researchers. Academic research in this area is bringing valuable insights into people attitudes and behavior on the social media (Klepek, 2017). To et al. (2007) showed that social interaction that occurs during online shopping is usually the main reason for customers to make an impulse purchase. Xiang et al. (2016) identified parasocial interaction as the main driving factor in impulse buying behavior. Aragoncillo and Orus (2018) showed in a study that the offline channel is slightly more encouraging of impulse buying than the online channel; factors that encourage online impulse buying explain this behavior to a greater extent than do discouraging factors. Yu et al. (2013) showed that the powers of online experience and friendships can make a website more valuable than a real community, but it depends entirely on corporate innovation and creativity. On the whole, social networks help improve user performance and maximize purchasing decision-making because of improved recommendation and data mining systems that are their important features. The results of a study by Stephen and Toubia (2009) showed that social networks transform customer-seller interaction from one-to-one into a community-based model, and the use of social networks for social commerce leads to business prosperity. So according to the explanation of the fourth hypothesis, it can be stated as follows:

H4: Parasocial interaction has a positive impact on the impulse buying behavior.

The Moderating Role of Social Class

The social class can be defined as a group of individuals with relatively uniform and permanent characteristics in society that differ in status, wealth, education, and values. Generally, members of a social class tend to live in a similar way, share common views and philosophies, and most importantly share the same patterns of purchase and consumption. In examining buyer behavior, the social class is a great indicator for identifying the type of buying behavior. People with higher social classes buy not only for necessity but also for fun. People from the upper classes use the price criterion less as a measure of quality and measure the quality of the product from its performance (Baker, 2008). Marketers need to explore different intrinsic factors of different consumer groups before going for full launch of impulsive products. consumers having varied degrees of intrinsic factors differ in their impulsive buying propensity and varied product combinations can be off good strategy to entice this consumer class and leverage higher sales (Sofi & Nika, 2017). The results of the studies of Ciunova-Shuleska (2012) and Baker & Hart (2008) indicate that the reasons for purchasing differ between different classes. Schinger (2017) concluded that in low-priced purchases that the product symbolically implies a lifestyle and values, the social class is a better indicator for predicting the impact of psychological and individual factors on purchasing decisions (Schinger, 2017; cited by Mohtasham Zadeh and Omid, 2017). So according to the explanation of the fifth hypothesis, it can be stated as follows:

H5: Social class has a moderating role in the relationship between the parasocial interaction and the impulse buying behavior.

The Moderating Role of Generation

Generational gap is a concept that addresses the significant psychological, social, cultural differences, and significant differences in insights, beliefs, perceptions, expectations, value orientations, and behavioral patterns between two generations at the same time (Sarokhani and Sedaghati Fard, 2009). The adult generation is less connected to technology than other generations, and the group is less likely to engage in social networking and prefer the planned shopping pattern. The younger generation that has witnessed the technological revolution and has grown up with technology is online 24 hours a day. Because of their high purchasing power and academic education, they are the main contributors to the parasocial interaction space and various social networks and fans of impulse buying (Pentax & Andrews, 2010; Khan et al., 2016). Among the recent foreign studies on intergenerational marketing is the research by Fernandez (2016) in Mexico, who showed that marketing researchers usually use US generational groups to define market segments. Results of Sundstrom et al. (2019) research reveal that young consumers' impulse purchases of fashion items online are often motivated by boredom. The findings of Santini et al. (2019) research demonstrated significant relation of antecedents and consequences of the impulse buying behavior, such as consumer impulsiveness, materialistic consumption, income, age, decision-making and positive emotions. So according to the explanation of the sixth hypothesis, it can be stated as follows:

H6: Generation has a moderating role in the relationship between the parasocial interaction and the impulse buying behavior.

The conceptual model of the research is presented as follows:

Figure 1. The Conceptual Model

Impulsive buying behavior has increased alongside the growth of digital transactions and technological advancements that simplify purchasing. Psychological studies have scientifically

demonstrated that e-commerce website design and enjoyable online shopping experiences can trigger positive emotions that drive impulsive buying behavior, especially in Z generation. Based on the literature review, it is determined that little research has been done on the concept of generational analysis, class analysis as the main drivers of impulse buying. The authors of this article aim to investigate the simultaneous effect of social class and generation on the relationship between extra social interaction and impulse buying behavior. The study will help both academicians and practitioners to identify, understand and implement the factors of social class and generation in future.

Research Methodology

The statistical population of this study consists of people active in Instagram social network, who have had intended to purchase from Instagram page users in the field of fashion (whether or not they bought) and have published information about their intention or purchase on this social network. Due to the lack of accurate information and statistics on the number of buyers of goods through the Instagram network, the number of samples was calculated with Sample Power and the sample size was estimated at 474 people. However, taking into account the drop in the questionnaire, the number of 950 users was selected based on the available sampling method from among the users who had purchased and left comments on selected Instagram pages, and by referring to Direct and sending electronic questionnaires to the sample. Selected required data were collected and finally the data related to 474 questionnaires out of 482 completed questionnaires were used. Therefore, the respondents' rate of survey was 482 out of 950 questionnaires. Collecting the required data in this online research was done using standard questionnaires. Data were collected using standard questionnaires. The questionnaire was divided into two sections. The first section was related to demographic characteristics, including questions about respondents' general characteristics, such as education, income, occupation, age, and gender. In this study, considering the age variable, generational analysis was done; In this way, the members of the statistical sample who are between 12 and 27 years old (born in 1995 to 2010) are part of generation Z, and people 28-42 years old (born in 1980 to 1994) are part of generation Y. A combination of the three indicators of income, education, and occupation was used to measure social class. The second part also includes specific questions about the research variables. The components of social features including three dimensions of other users' expertise (3 questions), liking other users (3 questions) and likeness of other users (3 questions), were extracted from Shen et al.'s (2010) research. Also, parasocial interaction (5 questions) was assessed using Thorson and Rodgers questionnaire (2006) and impulse buying behavior (4 questions) was assessed using Parboteeah questionnaire (2009). Data collection was done during two months. In order to analyze the data, partial least squares method was used to evaluate the validity and reliability of the questionnaire and to test the research model. Structural equation modeling is evaluated and interpreted in two stages using partial least square methods. The first step was the measurement model test and the second was structural model test.

Analysis and findings

Based on the results of the demographic characteristics analysis, the highest percentage of respondents is male respondents between 18 and 25 years of age, with BA degrees and 1-3 million Tomans monthly income and Private servant. The partial least squares method uses several criteria, including structural validity, diagnostic and convergent validity and reliability, to evaluate the fit of the measurement model. The construct validity has been tested by confirmatory factor analysis. Table 1 shows the results of this method, including factor loadings.

Table 1. Structural validity results (confirmatory factor analysis)

Latent variable	Observed variable/question	Factor loading
expertise of other users	Q ₁	0.843
	Q ₂	0.884
	Q ₃	0.908
Liking other users	Q ₄	0.910
	Q ₅	0.890
	Q ₆	0.827
Likeness of other users	Q ₇	0.773
	Q ₈	0.870
	Q ₉	0.798
Parasocial interaction	Q ₁₄	0.857
	Q ₁₅	0.847
	Q ₁₆	0.855
	Q ₁₇	0.825
	Q ₁₈	0.829
Impulse buying behavior	Q ₁₉	0.927
	Q ₂₀	0.934
	Q ₂₁	0.915
	Q ₂₂	0.887

The results in Table 2 show that for all items, the values of factor loadings are greater than the standard level of 0.5. Therefore, according to the reported values, it can be claimed that the questions in the questionnaire are of construct validity.

Table 2. Structural, diagnostic and convergent validity and reliability

Variable (Structure)	mean of the extracted variance (AVE)	Composite Reliability (CR)	Cronbach's Alpha Coefficient
other users' expertise	0.772	0.91	0.852
liking other users	0.767	0.908	0.848
likeness of other users	0.664	0.855	0.746
parasocial interaction	0.711	0.925	0.898
impulse buying behavior	0.839	0.954	0.936

In addition to construct validity, diagnostic validity, convergent validity and reliability are also addressed in Table 2. Values of this coefficient that are more than 0. Therefore, the structures have good composite reliability. Cronbach's alpha coefficients were generally higher than 0.7, indicating a high degree of internal consistency.

In order to measure divergent validity, the Fornell and Larker matrix (comparison of the correlation of a construct with its indicators versus the correlation of that construct with other constructs) was used. Fornell and Larker (1981) stated: Divergent validity is acceptable when the AVE for each construct is greater than the shared variance between that construct and other constructs (the square of the correlation coefficients between constructs) in the model. Based on this, acceptable divergent validity indicates that a construct in the model has more interaction with its indicators than with other constructs. The results are reported in Table 3. According to the results of Table No. 4, the values on the main diameter (root of AVE) are higher than the values below in each column, which indicates the higher correlation of each structure with its indicators in comparison with the correlation of that structure with other structures.

Table 3. Divergent validity, the Fornell and Larker matrix

Variable (Structure)	(UE)	(IBB)	(LOU)	(LU)	(PI)
other users' expertise (UE)	0.879				
impulse buying behavior (IBB)	0.855	0.916			
likeness of other users (LOU)	0.713	0.761	0.815		
liking other users (LU)	0.739	0.757	0.773	0.876	
parasocial interaction (PI)	0.86	0.872	0.759	0.818	0.843

One of the most important criteria for checking the fit of the structural model is the coefficient of determination (R^2). According to Figure 2 for the first model endogenous variable, i.e. parasocial interaction, R^2 is 0.819. Also, the coefficient of determination (R^2) for the second endogenous variable of the model, namely impulse buying behavior, was obtained to be 0.806. Therefore, with respect to the criterion values, the model generally has a good structural fit.

The GOF index in PLS can act as the overall fit indices of the model and can be used to check the validity or quality of the model in general. In the present study, GOF was 0.69. This indicates the optimal fit of the model when compared to the three values of 0.01, 0.25, and 0.36 as GOF weak, medium, and strong values.

Figure 2. Path coefficients and values of the coefficient of determination

Figure 3. T-student statistic values

The results of path coefficients along with t-student values and significance level are shown in Table 4.

Table 4. Hypothesis test results

Hypotheses	Path coefficient	t-statistics	Results
H ₁ : Other users' expertise → Parasocial interaction	0.522**	13.97	Confirmed
H ₂ : Liking other users → Parasocial interaction	0.33**	7.53	Confirmed
H ₃ : Likeness of other users → Parasocial interaction	0.132**	2.94	Confirmed
H ₄ : Parasocial interaction → impulse buying behavior	0.547**	11.45	Confirmed

* And ** are significant at 5% and 1%, respectively

The results in Table 4 showed that other users' expertise, liking other users and likeness of other users have a significant and positive impact on parasocial interaction with a standard coefficient of 0.522, 0.33 and 0.132. Therefore, the first to third hypothesis was confirmed. Also, parasocial interaction has a significant and positive impact on impulse buying behavior with a standard coefficient of 0.547. Therefore, the fourth hypothesis was confirmed.

In order to test the moderating role of variables, in addition to the direct effects, it is necessary to examine the effects of moderating variables on the relationship between variables. For this purpose, the relationships of variables in the research model were re-tested by adding social class and generation variables as moderating variables in the model and adding the path between the variables of parasocial interaction and impulse buying behavior. Considering social class, parasocial interaction has effect on impulse buying behavior with a standard coefficient of 0.098. It is, therefore, concluded that moderating role of social class in the relationship between parasocial interaction and impulse buying behavior has reduced the effect of parasocial interaction on impulse buying behavior and the fifth hypothesis was confirmed. Also, by generational analysis, i.e. considering generation, the variable of parasocial interaction has effect on impulse buying behavior with a standard coefficient of 0.109. It is, therefore, concluded that generation has a moderating role in the relationship between parasocial interaction and impulse buying behavior and the sixth hypothesis was confirmed.

Table 5. Hypothesis test results

Hypotheses	Path coefficient	t-statistics	Results
H ₅ : Parasocial interaction * Social class → impulse buying behavior	0.098**	2.86	Confirmed
H ₆ : Parasocial interaction * Generation → impulse buying behavior	-0.109**	3.2	Confirmed

* And ** are significant at 5% and 1%, respectively

Discussion

Uses and gratifications theory states that people actively choose and use media to satisfy individual needs. For example, while some may use social media to expand their

social circle, others may use it primarily to play games or share media content and sometimes to shop online. Jung et al. (2017) conducted interviews with people of generation x and y and from the middle social classes to understand how they use social networks. The results showed that the six main reasons for using social networks in this generation are: being in touch with family and friends, sharing photos, social monitoring, responding to family members, communication and curiosity. According to the study of Sheldon et al. (2021), the index of motives for using Instagram among the young generation and especially from high social classes, including the six scales of relationship monitoring, documentation, inspiration, self-promotion, entertainment and escape from reality / companionship and exploration for new products. And online shopping is impulsive. Therefore, people from different generations and social classes may have different motivations for using social media, including Instagram, and this leads to generational and class gaps in opposite fields, including impulse buying.

According to the finding of the first to third hypothesis of this study, social features has positive impact on parasocial interaction. Because attention to and reinforcement of related social features in the context of social commerce can lead to the formation of parasocial interaction. Social commerce by integrating user-generated content with the store enables businesses to reach global customers more efficiently than traditional retail stores. Customers can collaborate online, share product and service information and receive trusted advice from trusted people, making more informed and accurate purchasing decisions. As a result, the use of related social features, such as other users' expertise, liking other users, and likeness of other users, leads to the formation of parasocial interaction. The influence of this feature on the formation of parasocial interaction has also been confirmed in the studies of Xiang et al. (2016), Turban et al. (2011), and Ingar (2009). The result of the fourth hypothesis of the present study showed that increased parasocial interaction can lead to an increase in instant shopping behavior. Because customers are active in the context of parasocial interaction and have social relationships with other friends, members, and other online communities and retailers. They communicate, rate products, review others' opinions, participate in forums, share experiences, recommend products and services, and emotionally and informally support each other. Therefore, paying attention to social interactions in the social networking space can enhance customers' impulse buying intention on social networks. The impact of parasocial interaction on impulse buying behavior has been confirmed in the research of To et al. (2007), Dong Hee Shin (2014), Yu et al. (2013), Turban et al. (2011), and Wang and Lee (2011). According to the fifth hypothesis of this study, the social class plays a moderating role in the relationship between parasocial interaction and impulse buying behavior. Since human beings live in society, they are of behaviors that arise as a part of social interactions, whether face-to-face social interactions or virtual interactions via social networks. These interactions are somehow influenced by social factors, such as the social class to which the individual belongs. The social class influences consumers' personal purchasing decision-making process. Members of a social class have similar consumption patterns. The reasons for buying are different in different social classes. The type of consumption of goods and services is influenced by the social class. Also, the demographic characteristics of the members of each social class affect the consumption tendencies of each class, thus suggesting that the social class has a moderating role in the relationship between parasocial interaction and impulse buying behavior. This is in line with the findings of Ciunova-Shuleska (2012) and Baker & Hart (2008). According to the

sixth hypothesis of this study, the generation plays a moderating role in the relationship between parasocial interaction and impulse buying behavior. As generational distance leads to significant demands and gaps in experience, values and norms between generations, or, in general, to significant cultural differences and gaps between generation Z and Y, this intergenerational difference due to the less generation Y relationship with technology and generation Z engaging with social networks can lead to a different shopping pattern between the two generations. The results of the present study also showed that the intergenerational difference causes the effect of parasocial interaction on impulse buying behavior to be significantly changed. This is consistent with the results of studies by Pentax & Andrews (2010) and Khan et al. (2016).

Conclusions and Implications

In this study, an attempt was made to explain the relationship between parasocial interaction and impulse shopping behavior in the context of social commerce and examine the moderating role of social class and generation in the relationship between parasocial interaction and impulse shopping behavior which was not considered in previous research. The results showed that related social features had a positive effect on parasocial interaction. Parasocial interaction has a positive effect on impulse buying behavior. Also, social class and generation play a moderating role in the relationship between parasocial interaction and impulse buying behavior.

According to the findings of the study on the effect of related social features on parasocial interaction, managers and marketing planners are suggested to initiate the formation of parasocial interaction by considering and reinforcing related social features in the context of social commerce. Managers and planners can help build a more positive and enjoyable customer experience on social networks by creating the right infrastructure. Running campaigns that lead to the share of a shopping experience on social networks will also have a positive impact on enhancing the likeness and liking of other users in a parasocial interaction environment. Also it is suggested to focus on enhancing parasocial interaction by reinforcing its components and reducing constraints and related issues including: increasing coverage (attracting reliable views for most products), increasing depth (attracting trusted reviews for each product), increased penetration (displaying site visit content), increased trust (ensuring credible views are validly seen), increased ease of interaction, increased security through preventing sensitive information disclosure in the publicly available space and making significant efforts to combat social engineering attacks, reduced privacy violations, reduced fraud by identifying fake profiles on sites such as Instagram, Facebook, etc., increased intellectual property and limited copyright, increased content quality, and reduced content creator bias. Managers and planners should use strategies related to enhancing social interactions within social networks across generations that have different value priorities in order to reduce the intergenerational gap and social class differences affecting impulse buying behavior. Marketing managers can, therefore, attempt to increase the desirability of impulse buying between the adult generation and the different social classes, establish stable and transparent relationships with adult customers to increase their confidence and degree of trust in impulse buying on social networks; provide appropriate advertising and strive to instill a positive attitude towards impulse buying across generations, identify and understand the style and lifestyle of customers from different social classes and

generations in the target market, be aware of audience interests and motivations from different social classes and generations, design and create propaganda tailored to the needs and wants of customers from different social classes and generations, and select an advertising methods compatible with the mind of audience.

This study was conducted among users of Instagram and since the specific features governing this social networking space may be different from other social networks, replicating this research in other social networks may provide a better understanding of the marketing strategy selection mechanism. In recent years, many views have been raised about the need to develop a consumer decision model across generations as the effects of generational differences on individuals' behavior and decisions become more pronounced, but no model has been developed in Iran for the emerging and unknown generation of z, known as digitalis. A generation that will soon make up 40 percent of the world's consumers, and in Iran, nearly 30 percent of the population today. This generation has entered the age of money making and savings and investing experiences, with at least 15 years of market potential for these customers. It is, therefore, recommended to conduct research that provides the theoretical underpinnings for understanding the patterns of purchase of this emerging generation in the context of social commerce. In addition, future research can examine the factors influencing impulse buying behavior in other social business contexts, including telegram, Facebook, etc., the impact of other situational features, such as people's knowledge of the environment, payment methods, cashback policy, time constraint, financial constraint, and extent of search on consumer impulse shopping behavior in social trading context, relationship between objectivity and perceived antagonism with impulse shopping behavior in social business context, impulse buying rate in social commerce context in public relations such as national-religious holidays and festivals, survey of public trust of audience in advertisement on social business platforms, and replicate this research in a longitudinal and experimental manner, as well as exploratory-qualitative analysis and mixed methods.

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